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PROJECT TITLE: Community infrastructure to further open research software: A landscape analysis of needs, dependencies, and opportunities

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CO-PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS/CO-PROJECT LEADS

Kaitlin Thaney (Executive Director, Invest in Open Infrastructure)
Katherine Skinner (Research Lead, Invest in Open Infrastructure)

PROJECT GOAL

To build a comprehensive, shared understanding of the current state of the community and business/operations infrastructure for research software and its future potential

OBJECTIVES

Identify:

- Existing connections between different research software infrastructure initiatives, and where new connections can be built to advance sustainability and resilience of the ecosystem
- Areas in the ecosystem where there is overcrowding/excessive functional overlap, and where there are gaps, blockers, vulnerabilities, and/or critical dependencies that need addressing
- Indications of what helps infrastructure services and initiatives succeed in adding value to research software

PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

Desk research. Target interviews with project leads and stakeholders followed by synthesis and analysis.

EXPECTED PRODUCTS

Report identifying what we have learned from the project. Full presentation of findings. Integration of open research software infrastructures into Infra Finder

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

- Analysis and documentation of the current state of the research software landscape
- Identify gaps and vulnerabilities in the research software infrastructure ecosystem
- Identify opportunities to increase sustainability and impact of existing and future resources

Community infrastructure to further open research software: A landscape analysis of needs, dependencies, and opportunities

Kaitlin Thaney (Executive Director, Invest in Open Infrastructure)

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Proposal for Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. **Amount requested: \$149,994 USD**

1. What is the main issue, problem, or subject and why is it important?

Research software is a functional cornerstone of many scholarly disciplines, from the life sciences and physics to social sciences and humanities. Over the past decade, there have been significant increases in the availability and discoverability of research software, new roles such as research software engineers, and dedicated community efforts and organizations committed to training, capacity building, and growth of key practices necessary to develop and maintain research software for open research and scholarship.

The network of organizations providing key services, functions, and technical infrastructure for research software has grown significantly in size and complexity. Groups like the [Journal of Open Source Software](#) (JOSS), [rOpenSci](#), [pyOpenSci](#), and the [Software Sustainability Institute](#) (SSI) have introduced new opportunities for researchers to learn practices and access existing open source software to further their own research. Software repositories and registries ranging from the more general, multi-disciplinary (or agnostic) such as [GitHub](#), [GitLab](#), and [Zenodo](#) to more disciplinary-specific offerings including the [Astrophysics Source Code Library](#) (ASCL), the [Network for Computational Modeling in the Social and Ecological Sciences](#) (CoMSES Net), [bio.tools](#) / the [ELIXIR Tools and Data Services Registry](#) provide increased visibility and availability of research software and tools, while also presenting both opportunities and challenges in splintering of attention and discoverability, ownership and preservation concerns for large commercial players, and sustainability questions for community-specific solutions.

[OntoSoft](#), part of the [National Science Foundation's EarthCube Initiative](#) and [SciCrunch](#) out of the [FAIR Data Informatics Lab](#) at University of California, San Diego, are two additional examples of portals and services to make research software more discoverable while also providing support via advocacy and training offerings. Community infrastructure around research software, both digital and social, provides technologies and processes to facilitate collaborative development and testing (e.g. [GitHub](#)); containerization (e.g. [Singularity](#)); workflow management (e.g. [Snakemake](#)); review, curation, and publication (e.g. [Journal of Open Source Software](#)); discovery and (re)use (e.g. [Research Software Directory](#), [Emulation as a Service Infrastructure](#)); citation (e.g. [Citation File Format](#)); and archiving and preservation (e.g. [Software Heritage](#), [Software Preservation Network](#)) of research software and code. With robust community governance and engagement structures and processes, these community infrastructures help ensure that research software facilitates collaboration and fosters innovation and knowledge exchange, supports open, reproducible, and equitable research best practices, and empowers the research community.

Many, but not all, of these offerings work to support *open source* research software, which we consider to be most aligned with the needs and values of the research communities served, as well as the aims articulated by many of these organizations and initiatives regarding reproducibility, access, and open science. Additional nuance exists in the “openness” of research software as organizations explore intersections with the still-emerging Artificial Intelligence conversation, including GitHub’s launch of CoPilot and training on open source repositories on the platform which [elicited strong reactions](#) from the open source contributor community. The field is challenged to understand how AI is already altering practices within this

space and to predict what adaptations may be necessary to enable experimentation and collaboration with AI tools in future research software work.

Recent growth in organizations and initiatives aiming to serve the open research software community has led successful non-commercial initiatives to rely on grants-based support and membership models to keep these initiatives solvent. This work is not well coordinated, and the ecosystem is at risk of duplication and overlap between services. This is in contrast to for-profit offerings such as GitHub, which is owned by Microsoft and plays an outsized role in sharing of research software without the safeguards and community governance that many non-profit offerings provide.

The proliferation of diverse tools and platforms allows flexibility and choice but also leads to splintering and adopters' overwhelm as research communities struggle to understand which tools they should choose for their work. The development of domain-, institute- and country-/region-specific solutions, which aim to tailor to the needs of their stakeholders and communities, often results in the duplication of efforts as multiple groups independently develop and maintain similar solutions to common problems. These initiatives compete with each other for resources and attention; each running the risk of developing its own best practices and workflows, leading to a proliferation of approaches and lack of field-wide standardization, which in turn hampers collaboration and sustainability. This fragmentation complicates engagement between research communities, reduces interoperability, and poses additional security and maintenance challenges for this critical community infrastructure.

We believe a study to better understand the key players, needs, and dependencies in the space would produce useful insight into where there are opportunities for increased collaboration,

coordination, and shared support across efforts, with the aims of increasing the survivability of key initiatives, mitigating risk, and building towards more resilient models to ensure their future growth.

Recognizing this, more research stakeholders — funders, policymakers, institutional leadership, and others — are discussing and ideating around how to best invest in and support the research software ecosystem to ensure that it is sustainable and continues to center the needs of the research community. International declarations have been enacted (e.g. the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#)), national and institutional centers of excellence and policies have been established (e.g. the [US Research Software Sustainability Institute](#) (URSSI), the [Dutch national guide to research software management](#)), and funding instruments are developed and piloted (e.g. [CZI Essential Open Source Software for Science](#)).

IOI's recent work has surfaced and studied examples adjacent to the research software space where existing tools and technologies could potentially benefit from shared service models and collective organizational structures. IOI's current strategic engagements with preprint servers [arXiv](#), [bioRxiv](#) and [medRxiv](#); our data collection and analysis for [Infra Finder](#), and our deep work on financial and governance models are revealing the nearly universal experiences of adoption plateaus, precariously underpriced and undersubscribed membership models, and gaps in operational funding in open infrastructures today.

We see an urgent need to build a shared understanding, not just of single tools and communities, but of the state of the research software ecosystem that enables open, reproducible, and equitable research. This shared understanding will enable the research community and stakeholders to collectively identify gaps, vulnerabilities, and duplicative efforts,

and explore opportunities to coordinate and align efforts and investment to build a more resilient and sustainable infrastructure environment.

2. What is the major related work in this area?

Our proposed work and approach builds on the work of community working groups and initiatives, which have been advocating for the recognition of research software as research output, developing standards and best practices, building up capacity and professionalizing research software engineering (RSE), and coordinating investment. These include research software working groups within the [Research Data Alliance](#), [FORCE11](#) and [the Workshop on Sustainable Software Sustainability](#) (WoSSS); national and regional institutes such as the [Software Sustainability Institute](#), [URSSI](#), and [EVERSE](#); RSE networks such as the [UK RSE Society](#), [RSSE Africa](#), and [RSE Asia](#); advocacy and community cultivation initiatives such as the [Research Software Alliance](#), [the Turing Way](#), [Software Preservation Network](#), and [Open-Source Science](#) (OSSci); capacity building initiatives such as [the Carpentries](#) and [Code Refinery](#); and community infrastructures such as [rOpenSci](#), [ELIXIR](#), and [Galaxy](#).

While there have been broad calls for the community to explore common operational services and collaboration between different infrastructure services to reduce fragmentation (see e.g. Ithaka S&R's "[The Second Digital Transformation of Scholarly Publishing](#)"), we have not yet seen concrete efforts to identify candidates receptive to certain forms of interdependence, and then to bring together these stakeholders to co-create and test out models to build out these shared services.

The proposed work and approach uniquely complements the existing work of organizations and initiatives in the research software ecosystem, but adds to this landscape by employing an

evidence-based, co-creative, and outcome-driven approach to explore and test shared service models.

IOI is uniquely positioned to drive this work because:

- IOI sits at the intersection of a number of stakeholder communities, including funding bodies, infrastructure service providers, institutions, and research communities in North America, Europe, Latin America, and Africa. This has equipped us to build trust and intention into our work with stakeholders in this landscape, and further the representation of their needs, motivations, and priorities throughout our work.
- Through our engagement, partnerships, and research in scholarly communications, preprint services, and cloud infrastructure for research spaces, we have developed a deep understanding of the trends and needs in sustainable community infrastructure development. Our experience working in these adjacent cross-stakeholder spaces allows us to bring multifaceted examples and perspectives to bear on the research software problem space. We will use these to help facilitate the development of informed insights and solutions.
- IOI has established, tested, and refined a set of tools and processes to engage stakeholders in co-developing vision and strategy at a multi-institution or field level, including an alignment blueprint that can be used by these stakeholders to guide and track their independent work toward shared goals. These include stakeholder engagement and interview strategies and tooling to enable intentional and transparent outreach and community involvement, as well as research synthesis processes to effectively distill and communicate research insights.

3. What is the project? What are its goals and approach?

The goals of this project are (1) analyze and distill the characteristics and current state of the community infrastructure for research software amongst stakeholders in the research software space, and (2) collaboratively identify gaps and vulnerabilities, as well as explore opportunities to reduce fragmentation and duplicated efforts across organizations, increase utilization and impacts of resources, and further coordinate investments into shared resources and community-based solutions that can scale to support the ongoing development and maintenance of research software.

To build a comprehensive, shared understanding of the current state of the community and business/operations infrastructure for research software and its future potential, IOI will conduct a landscape analysis and needs assessment, focused on identifying:

- Existing connections between different infrastructure services and initiatives, and where new connections can be built to advance sustainability and resilience of the ecosystem;
- Areas in the ecosystem where there is overcrowding/excessive functional overlap, and where there are gaps, blockers, vulnerabilities, and/or critical dependencies that need addressing;
- Indications of what helps infrastructure services and initiatives succeed in adding value to research software.

A mix of desk research and stakeholder interviews and analysis will be used — an approach that IOI has previously deployed to build a strong understanding of what is most needed, feasible, and useful (e.g., [preprint infrastructure](#)). It will also build on previous landscape studies and other resources in related fields, including the [ReSA community landscape analysis](#), the [Map of Open-Source Science](#), and the [Open Scholarship Grassroots Community Networks](#). In this work, we will engage with key research software stakeholders, including infrastructure

service providers, funders, users, and advocacy and community groups to build a strong, grounded understanding of the evolution of research software support infrastructure.

Current and Planned Efforts to Ensure Diversity and Inclusion

Our team maintains a deliberate focus on diversity, equity, and inclusion that is physical (with team members across the US, Europe, and Africa) and ideological (with projects and programs incorporating diversity, equity, inclusion), and accessibility measures and criteria that ensure they are enriched with a broad spectrum of perspectives and voices and that they are accessible by the broadest possible audience. In this project, we will place special emphasis on surfacing and studying what research software tools and services are created in and supported by underrepresented communities (including those underrepresented in software generally, e.g., women, Black, Indigenous, and Latina/o/e communities, and in research software more specifically, e.g., scholars and developers in non-English speaking contexts and in lower and middle income economies (LMIE)). We regularly work with MetaDocencia to provide Spanish translation support and services as well as other translation support in French, which we expect to deploy in this project's interviews and communications. We also work with accessibility standards and experts to ensure that our research instruments and outputs are optimized for screen-readers and other accessibility tools.

4. Who are the key members of the project team?

Key project team members:

- **Kaitlin Thaney (Executive Director, IOI):** Overall project oversight and strategic direction of the project. Thaney served as the Endowment Director for the Wikimedia Foundation, directed the program portfolio for the Mozilla Foundation and was on the founding team for

Digital Science Thaney serves on the board of LYRASIS, a technology and services nonprofit serving higher education, libraries, archives and museums.

- **Katherine Skinner, PhD (Research Lead, IOI):** Strategic direction, developing the research protocols, conducting the desk research, stakeholder interviews and synthesis. Dr. Skinner is an open knowledge researcher-activist with deep commitments to community building, organizational resilience, and systems thinking. She helped found the Educopia Institute, where she provided scaffolding, training, and systems to support such collaborative groups as Library Publishing Coalition, MetaArchive Cooperative, BitCurator Consortium, C4DISC, Software Preservation Network, and Maintainers.
- **Gail Steinhart (Research Data Analyst, IOI):** Develop the research protocols, conduct the desk research and stakeholder interviews. Prior to IOI, as Head of Research Services at the Albert T. Mann Library, Cornell University, Steinhart has been involved in DataONE Community Engagement and Education Working Group and the arXiv.org leadership team, managing Cornell's institutional repository, and launching an open access journal hosting service at Cornell.
- **Lauren Collister, PhD (Engagement Coordinator, Infrastructure, IOI):** Develop research protocols, conduct the desk research and stakeholder interviews. Dr Collister will also develop an effective stakeholder engagement and communication strategy for this project. Prior to IOI, as the Director of the Office of Scholarly Communication and Publishing at the University of Pittsburgh, she led a diamond open-access publisher, advised on copyright and intellectual property, organized and advocated around labor issues in librarianship, and managed communication with editorial teams, developers, policymakers, and institutional leadership.
- **Jerry Sellanga (Engagement Coordinator, Networks, IOI):** Develop and execute communication strategy. Sellanga holds a Bachelor's degree in Environmental Studies

(Community Development) from Kenyatta University. Before joining IOI, Sellanga held senior roles in communication and marketing in the wildlife conservation, agriculture, and social impact sectors.

- **Madelyn Waterbury (Administrative Assistant, IOI):** Scheduling, operational and administrative support.
- **Jennifer Kemp (Research Strategist, Contractor):** Conducting interviews with key stakeholders, synthesizing recommendations, and providing strategic assistance to the research team. Kemp is currently working with IOI on strategic support engagements with arXiv, and brings a wealth of experience from her time at CrossRef, SpringerNature, HighWire Press, and IBM.

5. What is the work plan?

The proposed scope of work below aims to analyze the state of community infrastructure for research software; explore specific questions on ecosystem interoperability, gaps, and vulnerabilities; and identify opportunities for new types of collaboration or co-work. The work will be divided into three key activities:

- **Desk research** to ensure a clear and comprehensive understanding of the major players (funders, project teams, service providers, user communities) and the roles they currently play in the ecosystem.
- **Targeted interviews** to build understanding and relationships via a series of with leaders, supporters, and community organizers across stakeholder groups.
- **Reflection and assessment** of potential coordination mechanisms and ways to support the development of research software as a maturing field of practice, not just as individual services and products.

This system-level approach is key to the way we work and the possibilities we identify. In this project, we seek to develop practical solutions to current and future challenges faced by research software and the infrastructure that supports it so that the field evolves into a thriving open environment with community publishing and review infrastructure that is supported by strong business models and collaborative arrangements.

Desk research: IOI will begin by conducting desk research into the landscape of community infrastructure services providing review, publication, and other support for research software. We will use this opportunity to understand and contextualize research software as an object in its own right. This will include close attention to both public and nonpublic documentation related to the planning and conduct of governance, operations, finances, and community engagement work within individual services/communities and across the players in this maturing system. We will gain a strong initial understanding of the specific coordination, integration, and collaborative opportunities and challenges that may exist in this arena and identify appropriate targets for our next activity: interviews with key players. We will publish (CC-BY) a brief and a bibliography of sources based on our desk research.

- **Timeline & Milestones:** 1-2 months (Jul/Aug); desk research brief and bibliography. Metrics of success: Wide distribution and engagement with the brief and bibliography over the remainder of the project following its issuance, with success quantitatively measured by number of views, downloads, comments, and shares of the research brief, and number and diversity of interviewees identified for the next activity, and qualitatively by feedback and input from the research software and broader infrastructure community.

Targeted interviews with project leadership & stakeholders: We aim to conduct interviews with project leadership at pyOpenSci, rOpenSci, and JOSS, Software Heritage, GitHub, GitLab,

ASCL, ELIXIR, and CoMSENet, as well as stakeholders, e.g. governance and community members, funders, etc. identified in the desk research and additional conversations with external stakeholders. We will maintain anonymized briefs for each interview and will document our cross-interview findings in a brief report (CC-BY).

- **Timeline & Milestones:** 2-3 months (Sept/Aug/Sept/Oct); interviews brief. Metrics of success: Wide distribution and engagement with the brief over the remainder of the project period, with success quantitatively measured by number of views, downloads, comments, and shares of the interviews brief, and qualitatively by feedback and engagement from the interviewees and their communities, as well as from the research software and broader infrastructure community.

Synthesis and recommendations: A full report for the Sloan Foundation will synthesize learnings from desk research and interviews, documenting observations and recommendations. An aggregated and anonymized version for public dissemination (CC-BY and optimized for accessibility) will be produced. This landscape analysis will be the core output for this work, describing the current state of the field (including the entities and organizations operating in the space) and record the existing connections between research software infrastructure services and initiatives. This report will identify areas of overlap, overcrowding, and misalignment. It will conclude with our observations and recommendations of how to strengthen the system as a whole, not just as individual services. We will aim to identify several outcomes that are of high interest and benefit to many stakeholders. We will describe and chart out examples of work that could be undertaken by specific stakeholders independently of each other, but that would be visibly tracked at a meta-level across those stakeholders. Taken as a whole, these independent initiatives would measurably propel movement toward shared goals at the system level.

Based on the report, we will also prepare, present, record, and freely disseminate an open presentation of our findings, to which we will invite a range of funders, research software producers, research software infrastructure services, and other key stakeholder groups.

- Timeline & Milestones: 2 months (Nov/Dec). Metrics of success: Wide and deep engagement with the report, as well as attendance at/engagement with the presentation; interest in the pursuit of a follow-on project to convene and facilitate workshops in which stakeholders will devise and draft a formal roadmap towards shared, system-level goals.

6. What will be the output from the project?

Our work will result in two briefs and an extensive report describing 1) the current state of the research software support infrastructure environment and the players engaging in this space (including where they interact, overlap, duplicate efforts, and interoperate), and 2) Outcomes-based scenarios that our research shows as desirable to most stakeholders and specific steps that individual stakeholders might take to help move the system towards coherence. We will also present our findings openly and test our recommendations directly with the stakeholders in this space.

This output will lay the necessary groundwork for a prospective next phase of work: a series of collaborative, multi-stakeholder workshops where invited research software support service stakeholders identify which shared outcomes and future oriented goals might best serve the whole environment (whether from our report or otherwise), and then draft a roadmap to achieve those outcomes via streams of aligned-but-independent work by all invested stakeholders.

7. What is the summary justification for the requested funding?

The project will engage the skills and knowledge of five key IOI staff members, administrative assistance, and additional contractor research support. Kaitlin Thaney (10%) will provide overall project oversight. Katherine Skinner, PhD, (35%) will lead the design and implementation of research protocols and will engage in desk research, interviews, and reporting. Gail Steinhart and Lauren Collister (50% each) will lead the desk research, interviews, and initial synthesis and will assist with reporting, with support from Jennifer Kemp (research contractor). Jerry Sellanga (20%) will build and implement the project's communications plan, including publicizing the briefs and the report, and also coordinating the presentation. (Please note: Sellanga is listed as a contractor but works in a full-time capacity as core staff for IOI.)

Additionally we have \$4,000 USD of support included for administrative assistance, scheduling, and operations, and \$5,000 USD for equitable participation in the project, which includes accessibility needs, honoraria, and other accommodations.

Code for Science & Society provides comprehensive fiscal sponsorship, including financial back office support, grant administration, and human resources and operational support. COSts for that support are calculated at 15% on cash received, and are noted under "Indirect Costs".

8. What other sources of support has the proposer applied for or have in hand to support the project?

IOI is supported through a mix of philanthropic support and financial commitments from institutions and consortia-based organizations. Our current operations are supported predominantly via a 3-year \$3.4M grant from Arcadia, which covers the core salaries of our staff, administrative support, and some travel and convening support for targeted events. We are in our third year of that funding, which is currently set to conclude at the end of October 2024.

Additional staff support for Skinner, Steinhart, and Collister is provided in part by a NSF EAGER award to investigate “reasonable cost” in the post-Nelson memo US landscape, and a \$1M grant from the Mellon Foundation to support the build out of an infrastructure discovery and decision making tool, Infra Finder.

9. What is the status and output of current and/or previous Sloan grants?

In 2019, we received \$50,000 USD from the Sloan Foundation (Grant #: #G-2019-12547) as initial support to establish IOI as a network aimed at integrating and expanding open infrastructure initiatives. Outputs and outcomes included (1) building organizational capacity, resourcing, and governance, (2) conducting research and analysis including the [Future of Open Scholarship project](#), (3) providing strategic support and investment guidance, (4) enabling collective and coordinated action through events and funding pilots, and (5) begin work on a sustainability plan for IOI via diversified funding streams. Outputs included, but are not limited to, [decision making frameworks](#) and [recommendations](#) from the [Future of Open Scholarship project](#); [sustainability interviews](#) in collaboration with SPARC Europe; the second [Joint Roadmap for Open Science Tools Conference](#) and [Rapid Response Fund](#); initial development of a [framework](#) for gathering funding data; and [resources](#) to support building effective, anti-racist governance.

In 2021, the Sloan Foundation supported the [IOI Research Fellows](#) program pilot (Grant #: G-2021-14118), where we recruited two research fellows, Anne Britton and Teri Wanderi, who worked alongside IOI’s Research Data Analysts to expand and enhance our understanding of key issues related to furthering investment and the sustainability of open infrastructure in higher education and research. Britton explored [Wikidata as a tool for mapping investment flows for](#)

[open infrastructure](#), and Wanderi investigated [the impact of governments on the adoption of open infrastructure](#).

Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Plan

The demographic makeup of the project team (i.e., co/PIs, trainees, etc.) and strategies that will be used to further develop a diverse collaboration:

The core project team currently comprises [IOI leadership and team members](#) in the US, Mexico, and Kenya with backgrounds and experiences in open knowledge, open science, open source software, digital preservation, publishing, librarianship, and related spaces. IOI has been working with intention over the past 18+ months to deepen our research and understanding, relationships, staffing, [governance](#), and investments in Low and Middle Income Economies, as well as other Latin American and African countries. We aim to continue that work in the scope of this project, and strive to ensure we are actively seeking projects and leaders outside of North America and the UK, which can be predominantly represented in research software analyses.

The project team's experience and past record on issues of diversity, equity, and inclusion relevant to the proposed work:

Underlying all of IOI's work is a framework anchored in ensuring the work we do and recommendations we provide foster a healthier, more equitable and inclusive research ecosystem. This weaves through every aspect of our work, from our funding pilots to the research we produce. We highlight specific examples below:

- We launched the [Open Infrastructure Fund](#) to pilot and test a community-driven, participatory funding model to strengthen sustainability and resilience and increase the adoption of open infrastructure that underpins research and knowledge creation. The funding pilot began with a participatory budgeting process, and the scope of the pilot

was refined through a public funding design survey and target community conversations in Accra, Ghana and Buenos Aires, Argentina. To increase accessibility to funding to Low- and Middle-Income Economies (LMIEs), the open funding call was published in English and Spanish, and at least 60% of the funds were reserved for LMIE teams. We received 197 applications from 51 countries and worked with a panel of 55 community-nominated reviewers to select 8 projects in Latin America, Africa, Asia, and Europe to receive final funding.

- The [IOI Fund for Network Adoption](#) aims to deliver catalytic, multi-year funding to networks of institutions and researchers to identify and undertake practical steps towards furthering their adoption, implementation, and ongoing use of open infrastructures for data and content. To ensure that the Fund centres local research communities and their partners and to facilitate collaboration and exchange of learnings across geographical and cultural contexts, we designed and developed a targeted network engagement strategy focussed on Africa, Latin America, and North America, building on IOI's existing work and prioritizing the inclusion of networks from regions historically under-resourced in open infrastructure development. To date, we have engaged with 30+ networks, including 10 networks in Latin America and 14 in Africa, as part of this strategy.
- As part of a consortium delivering a project titled "[a collaborative interactive computing service model for global communities](#)", IOI is responsible for co-designing a governance and sustainability model that will facilitate power sharing and encourage ongoing collaborative engagement from ~20 user communities in Latin America and Africa.

- Through [exploratory regional research](#) in 2023, we sought to better understand the initiatives, people, and issues involved in scholarly infrastructure in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Combining desk research and 21 semi-structured interviews in English and Spanish, this research shed light on the different characteristics of infrastructures serving the differing regions, as well as strengths, enablers, threats, and opportunities in advancing research infrastructure development in each region.

Current or planned strategies to ensure an equitable and inclusive work environment within the project team, and resources we will draw on to support these strategies:

At IOI, we believe that for any organization that values equity and openness, the structures and processes governing the organization are critical for ensuring the organization acts by its values and puts its belief into practice. Since our founding, we have been [evolving our governance](#) with the goal to hold ourselves to account for the trust we seek to build and maintain within our team and governance and with our stakeholders.

Some of our current strategies include:

- Improving our data and digital security practices: after an audit of our existing data collecting and processing practices, we have established a [data privacy policy](#) (updated annually), a vendor diligence process, and an internal protocol for collecting, handling, and storing sensitive research data. From January to February 2024, the IOI team has also undergone digital hygiene and security training.
- Establishing a [Conflict of Interest Declaration and Policy](#).
- Developing and implementing a [Code of Conduct](#) across our engagement and research efforts.

- Public documentation on governance and organizational history, including our [orientation packet](#) and [governance roster and charters](#).

Budget and Detailed Budget Justification

The costs outlined in the prepared budget largely support IOI staff and contractor time to conduct the outreach, engagement, and deep research and strategic analysis for this project. Jennifer Kemp and Jerry Sellanga are contractors with IOI operating in a part- and full-time capacity as functional team members. Madelyn Waterbury provides administrative assistance in scheduling, processing of contracts, and other operational support necessary to run effective studies such as this one.

Full-time, benefitted staff are separated out to denote the 25% fringe benefit addition. We also have over the course of this six-month project a starting salary as well as an adjusted salary to denote annual cost of living increases that happen in July/August of the calendar year for our organization.

An additional \$5,000 USD is allocated to equitable participation support, including honoraria for participants for their time and accessibility and translation support as needed.

Lastly, \$22,499 USD is included as our fiscal sponsorship fee for Code for Science & Society's comprehensive back office and administrative support as our organizational home.

APPENDIX: Attention to Diversity Statement

Code for Science & Society (CS&S), IOI, and all CS&S' Sponsored Projects are committed to meaningful equity and inclusive organizational practices. Science and technology are human endeavors, subject to influence by the biases of people. In the pursuit of science, people have often replicated power structures that reinforce the disenfranchisement and exclusion communities. In the American context, this has historically centered on the exclusion of marginalized communities from work in scientific and technical communities. CS&S strives to be a community leader on issues around meaningfully inclusive public interest technology across domains. CS&S does this through work with our Sponsored Projects and Collaborative Communities Programs.

When working with sponsored projects, CS&S focuses on helping projects grow sustainable, inclusive culture through evolving governance, working transparently, encouraging open dialogue around building leadership skills. Our Collaborative Communities program focuses on building capacity on the open source ecosystem. The Open Source Alliance for Open Scholarship [Handbook Project](#), includes a [frequently referenced definition](#) of Open Scholarship, where equity and inclusion are central. Ongoing work with inclusion professionals [DeEtta Jones & Associates](#) will focus on the challenging conversations about inclusion that are happening (and often not happening) in the open source and science space. Our work with DeEtta Jones [is summarized here](#).

As a nonprofit home of multiple sponsored projects, CS&S will oversee project leaders and teams, who will also collaborate with staff at outside organizations. By centering transparency and governance with our projects and leaning into organizational and community growth, we hope to continue to lead as a voice for meaningful inclusive practices in open source and science. Our direct plans, as well as examples of how we incorporate diverse representation our projects:

1. **Diversity in our Collaborators:** When collaborating with partners, we recruit diverse perspectives to participate, be it through user-centered design processes, governance, or to speak to our community.
2. **Equity and Representation in Staffing:** We offer structure and benefits to support our project's abilities to recruit and retain talented people from all backgrounds.
3. **Centering Inclusion in the Project Governance:** CS&S has been actively engaged in supporting open source communities to question, iterate, and mature governance models. For example, in 2020 we engaged DeEtta Jones & Associates to help us to develop and implement governance processes for ourselves and our sponsored projects that center meaningful equity and anti-racist values.
4. **Proactively Seeking Opportunities to Engage with the Global Community:** It can be hard for small projects on limited budgets to adjust to the needs of a growing community. There are unique funding opportunities for open projects to get expert diversity support. As an example, PREreview was selected to convene a working group of international experts at 2019 TriangleSci to focus on [bringing equity and diversity to peer review](#), and a Wellcome Trust grant [specifically focused on Diversity and Inclusion](#).

APPENDIX: List of Citations

References are included inline above.

APPENDIX: CONFLICTS OF INTEREST/SOURCES OF BIAS

Conflict of Interest Statement

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) interacts with many collaborators and stakeholders in its work. In these conversations, some may have overlapping interest with parts of IOI's strategy and operations that bias their contributions or otherwise compromise their independence, particularly when it comes to making funding and resourcing recommendations or working with external partners. This might apply to funding bodies, university leaders, members of the infrastructure community, and supporting organizations.

IOI's Conflict of Interest Policy & Declaration applies to all IOI staff, governance members, contractors, and consultants. In participating in this process, individuals consent to have this information be disclosed to IOI and made available publicly on our website (<https://investinopen.org>), in line with IOI's commitment to transparency and accountability.

The IOI governance structure, including the Steering Committee, all other Committees and temporary or permanent working groups have a strict recusal process when individual infrastructure projects are involved in a decision-making process that could impact their own funding opportunities.

While these conflicts can't be completely eliminated we recognize that disclosing these potential conflicts in an open and transparent way helps establish accountability and build trust. IOI's Conflict of Interest Declaration and Policy is an important piece of information to help us understand the potential external influence in the form of Board representation, involvement in similar initiatives, and other ties to funding and funding bodies that could interfere with the independent, reliable, and authoritative engagement we seek with our partners. Additional

documentation on this policy and public declarations of existing conflicts can be found at <https://hackmd.io/@investinopen/conflict-of-interest>.

APPENDIX: INFORMATION PRODUCTS

Information Products

The Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) will produce documents, databases, surveys and other landscape analysis tools, and conduct workshops and interviews with a wide range of stakeholders. All materials will be made available under a CC-BY license with the exception of sensitive personnel and/or funding information. It is the stated goal of the IOI project that these outputs be participatory in nature and of use to the wider community.